

Post Hoc Analysis of English Teaching Approaches on Literacy Engagement and Performance

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Abstract. This study examined the implementation of English teaching approaches and their impact on learners' literacy engagement and performance in Sarangani District, Davao Occidental. A quantitative descriptive-comparative design was used, involving 146 teacher and learner respondents through a validated survey. The English teaching approaches were categorized into three components: pedagogical strategies, teacher experiences, and classroom environment. Learners' literacy engagement and performance were measured through self-reported literacy skills, peer interaction, reading comprehension, fluency, and motivation. A one-way ANOVA indicated a significant difference in literacy outcomes based on teaching approaches, $F(2, 143) = 5.023$, $p = .008$. Post hoc analysis revealed that the classroom environment significantly influenced literacy engagement and performance compared to pedagogical approaches ($p = .006$), with no significant differences noted among other components. Findings affirm that effective English instruction is multidimensional and that a supportive classroom environment is essential for enhancing learner outcomes. The study recommends improving classroom conditions alongside pedagogical development to foster better English literacy in public schools.

KEY WORDS

1. English teaching approaches
2. literacy engagement
3. classroom environment

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1. Introduction

English teaching approaches and their impact on literacy engagement and performance among learners present several challenges in educational settings. One significant challenge is the diversity of student learning styles and abilities, making it difficult for a single pedagogical approach to engage all students effectively. Some learners may thrive in a communicative language teaching environment emphasizing interaction; others may struggle with this method and require more structured, traditional approaches to grasp foundational concepts. Varying levels of literacy skills within a classroom can lead to disparities in engagement, as students with lower proficiency may feel overwhelmed and disengaged from activities that assume a higher level of competence. Teachers often face constraints such as limited resources, insufficient training in modern teaching methodologies, and pressure to meet standardized testing benchmarks, which can hinder their ability to implement innovative strategies effectively. These challenges collectively impact students' motivation to learn, their participation in literacy activities, and ultimately their performance in English literacy, highlighting the need for more

tailored and flexible teaching approaches that consider the diverse needs of all learners. The international mobility of knowledge workers, as reflected in the vast numbers of international (or immigrant) scholars, help provide the intellectual infrastructure of several higher learning and research institutions worldwide. Although the large numbers involved reflect the apparent success of this phenomenon, international scholars face hidden challenges (Hutchison, et.al., 2021). Shotte (2024) shared that English is the most widely spoken language in the world. This fact deserves serious consideration for educators at all levels of the education system, but more so for those who are tasked with teaching English to learners whose mother tongue is not English. Globalization, the internationalization of education, and migratory trends are largely responsible for narrowing the interconnection of world peoples via various means. For this very reason, English language pedagogical issues exist in multilingual countries and in countries with a migrant multilingual population. The author explores the value of, and benefits to be gained from, employing tailor-made pedagogical approaches in English language teaching. It contends that the all-embracing educational landscape necessitates a parallel move with the fast-changing times. It also explains why and how pedagogical spaces should be widened and narrowed. The discussion draws from a wide literature base, research findings, and personal experiences but zeros in on theoretical frameworks such as constructivism, social constructivism, and scaffolding. Meanwhile, with globalization increasingly defining the world, international students are undertaking an important agentic role in terms of communicating with different cultures. Therefore, their experiences significantly reveal the pedagogical practices between different country settings. Zhang (2024) attempted to compare pedagogical practices between the UK and China by examining their cultural origins and potential connections with pedagogical assumptions, placing them on a spectrum of teacher/learner-centered pedagogy. Combined with the perspective of Chinese international students studying in the UK, it captures the lived experiences of the actual classroom differences experienced by these students. It concludes that each pedagogy has its benefits and drawbacks, respectively, and fits its cultural context. Therefore, it is not possible for one particular educational system to completely 'borrow' pedagogic practice. In the Philippines, as experts in English language teaching, Jung and Choe (2024) consider themselves equal to, or even superior to, native English-speaking teachers, which they attribute to their language proficiency, pedagogical skills, and content-based teaching. In their role as educational caretakers, they prioritize their students' well-being, providing motivation for English language learning and offering emotional support. Furthermore, they identify themselves as international teachers, deliberately choosing BGC as their career destination to foster multiculturalism and global citizenship. The authors scrutinize the roles of FETs, frequently categorized as "non-native teachers," within the context of globalization. Tarrayo (2023) revealed that to effectively teach, the implementation of gender mainstreaming in education has remained vague. Also, there is a gap in the literature regarding informed accounts of teachers, particularly English language teachers, in their attempts to mainstream gender-and-development (GAD) education in Philippine schools. Findings indicate that teachers are ready to integrate a gender perspective into their teaching; however, concrete frameworks, curriculum materials, teacher education, and institutional support are crucial, given the sensitive ethical concerns that consideration of gender may generate among educators, students, and the wider community. With the growing acknowledgment of schools as potential sites for making gender equity, justice, and fairness possible, incorporating a gender perspective in

education has become imperative. The field of English language teaching (ELT) has also been part of this development, with issues of gender and sexuality receiving considerable attention. Tarrayo and Salonga (2023) state that teachers have positive views about queering ELT and, in fact, find it necessary for fostering an inclusive classroom and stimulating students' critical thinking. However, the teachers also report a lack of models, their own limited knowledge of queer concepts, and possible resistance from stakeholders as challenges that ultimately need to be faced for a genuine integration of the gender, specifically queer, perspective in the field of Philippine English Language Teaching. Teaching English in Davao Occidental presents several challenges affecting educators and students. One of the primary obstacles is the diversity in students' language backgrounds and proficiency levels. Many learners come from various linguistic and cultural backgrounds, making it difficult for teachers to implement a one-size-fits-all approach to instruction. Additionally, limited resources, such as textbooks and technology, hampers teachers' ability to deliver engaging and effective lessons. In many schools, inadequate infrastructure and facilities further exacerbate the situation, creating an environment that may not be conducive to language learning. Thus, this paper is presented.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—Several educational theories provide a solid foundation for understanding and guiding the study, which explores the impact of different pedagogical approaches on literacy engagement and performance metrics in Davao Occidental. Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory highlights the role of modeling and observational learning in teaching. For teachers, this means that their instructional methods and classroom interactions serve as powerful models for students. Teachers can significantly influence student motivation and performance by demonstrating effective literacy practices

and fostering an environment of collaboration (Zhang, 2024). Professional Development Theory emphasizes the importance of continuous learning for educators. This theory advocates for ongoing training and support to help teachers refine their instructional strategies and adapt to diverse student needs. By engaging in professional development, teachers can enhance their pedagogical skills and better implement effective literacy teaching approaches, improving student outcomes (Hutchison et al., 2021). Lastly, the Self-Determination Theory is crucial in understanding how teachers' motivations affect their teaching practices. When teachers feel a sense of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in their professional roles, they are more likely to engage enthusiastically in innovative teaching methods that enhance student literacy. By focusing on these theories, the study can better assess how teachers' beliefs, practices, and professional growth directly influence their students' literacy engagement and performance metrics (Shotte, 2021). Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. The study examining the impact of teaching approaches on literacy engagement and performance metrics identifies two primary sets of variables: independent variables (IVs) and dependent variables (DVs). The independent variables include teaching English approaches, encompassing pedagogical strategies, teacher experience levels, and classroom environments. These variables are critical as they directly influence how literacy is taught and learned. For example, constructivist approaches encourage active student participation, while traditional methods may prioritize rote memorization. The dependent variables consist of literacy engagement and performance, measured through self-reported literacy skills, peer interaction, reading comprehension, fluency, and motivation for reading. These metrics are vital for assessing the effectiveness of different teaching strategies on students' literacy outcomes. The application of relevant theories

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

enhances the understanding of how these variables interact within the study; Social Learning Theory emphasizes the significance of peer interaction, suggesting that students learn effectively through observing and engaging with their classmates. This aspect is crucial when considering how collaborative learning impacts literacy metrics.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, the researcher outlines the essential processes and steps required to conduct the study. These include selecting the study design, determining the respondents and sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data gathering, outlining the procedure, addressing ethical considerations, and conducting data analysis. These steps are crucial to ensuring the appropriateness and correctness of the study and producing sound data collection, analysis, and interpretation.

2.1. Research Design—The research design for this study is a quantitative, comparative analysis to assess the effect of different English teaching approaches on Literacy Engagement and Performance metrics in Sarangani District, Davao Occidental. The One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is utilized to analyze the differences among English teaching approaches (Creswell, 2014) and the dependent variable, the Literacy Engagement and Performance metrics. One-way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) is a statistical method that is highly applicable to the study on "Post Hoc Analysis of English Teaching Approaches on Literacy Engagement and Performance" as it allows for comparing means among multiple groups to determine if there are statistically significant differences between them. In the study, the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is employed as the primary statistical method to evaluate the im-

pact of various teaching approaches on students' literacy engagement and performance metrics. This statistical technique is particularly suitable for comparing the means of three or more independent groups, allowing researchers to assess whether the pedagogical approaches employed in different classrooms lead to significant differences in student outcomes. In the study context, each independent variable namely, the specific teaching approaches, teacher experience levels, and classroom environments—represents distinct groups of students receiving different instructional methods. By collecting data on literacy engagement and performance metrics from these groups, the One-Way ANOVA enables the researcher to determine if the variations in teaching methods result in statistically significant differences in students' literacy outcomes. If significant differences are found, post hoc tests can be conducted to identify which specific groups differ from one another, thereby providing a deeper understanding of the effectiveness of each teaching approach. Ultimately, the application of One-Way ANOVA in this study validates the influence of pedagogical strategies on literacy development and contributes to evidence-based decision-making in educational practices, guiding teachers and school leaders in selecting effective instructional methods to enhance student learning.

2.2. *Ethical Consideration*—The ethical consideration section of this study will address the key principles that ensure the protection and well-being of the teacher-respondents involved. This includes adhering to social values, informed consent and assent, vulnerability of research respondents, privacy and confidentiality, risks, benefits, and safety, justice, transparency, qualification of the researcher, conflict of interest, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement.

Social Value

I believe that every student deserves the opportunity to succeed, and this study addresses

the critical challenges in literacy education. Ethically, it is my responsibility to promote teaching methods that cater to the diverse needs of students, particularly those who may struggle with literacy. By contributing to evidence-based practices, I hope to empower teachers, school heads, and policymakers to make informed decisions that positively impact student learning and development. Ultimately, my goal is to foster a more educated and capable community, reflecting my commitment to social justice and the belief that education should serve the best interests of all students.

Informed Consent and Assent

Since my participants are teachers, I will ensure they are fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits before they agree to participate. I will provide detailed information in clear and accessible language to facilitate their understanding, allowing them to make an informed decision. Additionally, I will obtain their consent voluntarily, ensuring that they feel comfortable and can withdraw at any time without any negative consequences. By prioritizing informed consent, I aim to respect the autonomy of the teachers involved in my study, fostering a transparent and ethical research environment. This commitment to ethical practices not only protects the rights of participants but also enhances the credibility and integrity of my research.

Vulnerability of Research Respondents

I recognize the vulnerability of my research participants, who are teachers. Educators may feel pressured regarding their professional practices and performance, especially when the study evaluates the effectiveness of different teaching approaches. This awareness compels me to approach the research with sensitivity and care. I am committed to creating a safe and supportive environment for the teachers participating in my study. I will ensure that their identities remain confidential and that their responses are anonymized to minimize any po-

tential anxiety about judgment or repercussions. Furthermore, I will emphasize that participation is entirely voluntary, allowing them to withdraw at any time without impacting their professional standing. By acknowledging their vulnerability and protecting their interests, I aim to uphold ethical standards in my research while fostering trust and collaboration with my participants.

Privacy and Confidentiality

I prioritize the privacy and confidentiality of my participants, who are teachers. I understand that they may be sharing personal insights and experiences related to their teaching practices, and it is essential to protect this information. To ensure confidentiality, I will anonymize all data collected from the teachers, assigning codes instead of using their names. This approach will help safeguard their identities and maintain their privacy throughout the research process. Additionally, I will store all data securely and limit access to only those directly involved in the study. I will also communicate to the participants that their responses will be used solely for research purposes and will not be shared in any identifiable form. By committing to these ethical practices, I aim to foster a trustworthy environment where teachers feel comfortable sharing their perspectives without fear of exposure or negative consequences.

Risk, Benefits and Safety

I carefully consider the risks, benefits, and safety of my participants, who are teachers. I recognize that participating in research can sometimes involve stress or discomfort, particularly when discussing their teaching practices and their effectiveness. To mitigate risks, I will provide clear information about the study's purpose and procedures, ensuring that teachers feel prepared and informed. I will emphasize that their participation is voluntary and that they can withdraw at any time without any repercussions. The benefits of participating in this study include contributing valuable insights that can lead to improved teaching practices and

ultimately enhance student outcomes. Additionally, by engaging in this research, teachers may gain a deeper understanding of effective pedagogical approaches that could benefit their own professional development. I am committed to ensuring a safe and supportive environment throughout the research process. By addressing potential risks and highlighting the benefits, I aim to foster trust and encourage open participation among the teachers, reinforcing the ethical integrity of my study.

Justice

I recognize that the insights and perspectives of all teachers are valuable for understanding effective pedagogical approaches. Therefore, I will make efforts to include a diverse range of teachers in my study to capture a wide array of experiences and viewpoints. Additionally, I will ensure that the benefits of the research extend to all participants, allowing them to gain insights that can enhance their teaching practices and contribute to their professional development. I aim to promote fairness in the research process by upholding the principle of justice, ensuring that every teacher's voice is heard and respected. This commitment not only reinforces the ethical integrity of my study but also contributes to a more inclusive understanding of effective literacy instruction in junior high school settings.

Transparency

I believe that open communication with my participants, who are teachers, is essential for building trust and ensuring their comfort in sharing their insights and experiences. I will clearly explain the study's purpose, methodology, and how their data will be used. This includes outlining the benefits and potential risks associated with participation, so teachers can make informed decisions about their involvement. Additionally, I plan to share the findings of the research with the participants once the study is complete, allowing them to see the impact of their contributions. By committing to transparency, I aim to create an ethical research en-

environment where teachers feel valued and respected. This openness enhances my study's integrity and fosters a collaborative atmosphere that encourages honest feedback and meaningful participation.

Qualification of the Researcher

I have a background in education and a strong understanding of pedagogical theories, which enables me to approach this research with both knowledge and sensitivity. My experience in working with educators allows me to appreciate the challenges they face in their teaching practices. I am committed to conducting this study ethically and rigorously, ensuring that I adhere to the highest standards of research integrity. Additionally, I plan to engage in ongoing professional development to stay informed about best practices in educational research, which will enhance my ability to analyze and interpret the data effectively. By demonstrating my qualifications and commitment to ethical research practices, I aim to foster confidence among the teachers participating in my study, reassuring them that their contributions will be valued and respected throughout the research process.

Conflict of Interest

To maintain the integrity of the research, I will disclose any relationships or affiliations that could be perceived as influencing the study's outcomes. I understand that the teachers may have personal or professional stakes in the research findings, which could impact their willingness to participate honestly. To mitigate this, I will emphasize that their involvement is voluntary and that their responses will remain confidential and anonymous. Additionally, I will ensure that I remain objective in my data collection and analysis, focusing solely on the evidence without allowing any biases to influence my interpretations. By addressing conflicts of interest transparently, I aim to uphold ethical standards in my research, reinforcing trust with the teachers and ensuring that the study's find-

ings are credible and valid. This commitment not only safeguards the research process but also respects the professionalism of the teachers involved.

Adequacy of Facilities

This includes having access to appropriate resources, such as a conducive environment for conducting surveys and interviews, as well as the necessary technology to collect and analyze data effectively. I understand that inadequate facilities can hinder the research process and affect the quality of the data collected. Therefore, I will take the necessary steps to ensure that I have access to suitable locations for meetings with participants and that any tools or technology I use are reliable and user-friendly. This commitment to providing an adequate research environment not only supports the integrity of my findings but also respects the time and effort of the teachers participating in my study.

Community Involvement

I understand that teachers play a vital role in shaping the educational landscape, and their insights can contribute meaningfully to the wider community. To promote community involvement, I will actively seek feedback from teachers during the research process and after sharing the findings. This engagement ensures that their voices are heard and valued, fostering a sense of collaboration. I plan to present the results of my study to the local education community, including school heads and other stakeholders, to highlight the effective pedagogical approaches identified through the research.

2.3. Research Respondents—Using Slovin's formula with a population of 230 teachers from the Sarangani District, Davao Occidental Schools Division, and a margin of error of 0.05, the required sample size for the study is approximately 146 respondents. The respondents will be teachers from schools within the Sarangani District who teach English subjects. These schools include Alberto Olarte Sr. NHS, Mabila ES, Tucal EL, Angel F. Olarte

ES, Tinina ES, and Lipol ES. By selecting 146 respondents, the study ensures a representative sample that maintains statistical validity while reflecting the diverse perspectives of teachers across the district. This sample will allow for meaningful insights into the research objectives while maintaining practical feasibility in data collection. The researcher proportionately distributed the samples to be determined as respondents from the respective schools, and the respondents will be informed through online platforms and face-to-face, considering the availability of Wi-Fi connections. They were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. In my study, the respondents are English teachers from both elementary and junior high schools, and their qualifications play a crucial role in the research's validity. These teachers typically possess a bachelor's degree in education, with a specialization in English or a related field, ensuring they have a solid foundation in language instruction and pedagogy. Many have undergone professional development training to stay updated on current teaching methodologies and curriculum standards. Additionally, the respondents often have varying levels of teaching experience, ranging from novice teachers to seasoned educators with several years of classroom practice. This diversity in experience allows for a rich exchange of perspectives on effective pedagogical approaches. Furthermore, their involvement in school-based professional learning communities and workshops indicates a commitment to continuous improvement in their teaching practices. By selecting qualified English teachers as respondents, I aim to gather meaningful insights into the effectiveness of different pedagogical approaches on literacy engagement and performance metrics, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of English education in elementary and junior high schools.

2.4. Research Instrument—In this research study, the researcher adopted survey instruments from Zhang's (2021) study on A Comparison between Pedagogical Approaches in UK and China and other sources like Hutchison et.al. (2021) on A Survey of Expected versus Actual Pedagogical Challenges Experienced by International Professors. Contents of the respective tools were adopted and modified based on the problem statement, the variables, and the study's contention. The researcher made a dedicated effort to collect and analyze literature to identify concepts that informed the content and provided support for the instrument and its associated components. This careful process resulted in question items addressing potential threats to the study's validity. The survey questionnaire had two parts. One part determined the extent of English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment. Likewise, the second part of the survey measures the extent of literacy engagement and performance as perceived by the teachers. Further, the survey statements will be subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 confidence level. Cronbach's alpha is a measure of scale reliability that assesses the degree to which survey items correlate, thus providing a unified measure of a construct. A value above 0.70 is generally considered acceptable, with values above 0.80 indicating good reliability and values above 0.90 signifying excellent reliability (Tabachnik and Fidel, 2019). To assess the internal consistency of the instrument used in measuring English teaching approaches, Cronbach's Alpha was computed based on the responses to the five-item Likert scale comprising the pedagogical strategies domain. The Frequentist reliability analysis produced a Cronbach's Alpha () of 0.850, with a 95A Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.850 indicates a high level of internal consistency among the items in the scale. According to conventional benchmarks (Field,

2021; Taber, 2018), an alpha coefficient above 0.80 suggests that the instrument items measure a cohesive construct, thus affirming the scale’s reliability for capturing pedagogical strategies. The narrow confidence interval further supports the precision of the reliability estimate, suggesting that similar reliability levels would be obtained in repeated measurements or different samples from the same population. This strong internal consistency justifies aggregating the five items into a composite mean score, which was used to represent the extent of pedagogical strategy implementation in subsequent

statistical analyses, including its categorization into Low, Moderate, and High levels. Moreover, the high reliability coefficient aligns with best practices in instrument validation and supports the interpretability of the data generated from this section of the survey instrument (Cohen, Manion, Morrison, 2022). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert-type scale to determine the extent of English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation for English Teaching Strategies

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment are oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment are rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment are not manifested

To facilitate inferential analysis, particularly applying One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Likert-scale responses in the research instrument were transformed into cat-

egorical variables. The instrument employed a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree/ Not Manifested/Not Extensive) to 5 (Strongly Agree/Very Extensive/ Highly Man-

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation for Literacy Engagement and Performance

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The literacy engagement and performance is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The literacy engagement and performance is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The literacy engagement and performance is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The literacy engagement and performance is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The literacy engagement and performance is not manifested

ifested) to assess the extent of implementation of English teaching approaches. Each item within the domains—pedagogical strategies, teaching experience levels, and classroom environment—was scored accordingly. Composite mean scores were then computed for each domain per respondent. To enable group comparison, particularly to address Research Problem 3 on whether significant differences exist in learner outcomes based on teaching approach levels, the continuous mean scores were converted into ordinal categories: Low, Moderate, and High. This transformation was conducted using quantile-based binning, specifically the tertile method, which divides the data into three approximately equal-sized groups. Respondents with lower composite scores were grouped under “Low,” those with mid-range scores under “Moderate,” and those with higher scores under “High.” This categorization approach is justified on both methodological and interpretive grounds. Methodologically, transforming Likert-derived means into ordinal groups is acceptable when the primary goal is to compare distinct levels of implementation or perception across categories (Field, 2021). It also aligns with the assumptions of One-Way ANOVA,

which requires a categorical independent variable and a continuous dependent variable. Interpretively, this technique enhances clarity in reporting and facilitates meaningful policy or instructional implications by identifying which level of implementation is associated with improved learner outcomes (Tabachnick Fidell, 2019). Moreover, such categorical treatment of Likert-scale aggregates is widely practiced in educational and social science research, especially when exploring group-level differences or patterns (Cohen, Manion, Morrison, 2022). In this study, the transformation ensured that the statistical procedures applied were technically appropriate and aligned with the research problem’s practical orientation.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The guidelines for this process adhere to the policies of The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. As part of the formal request, researchers delineate their intentions regarding data collection, analysis, and dissemination, aligning these with the overarching research goals. This communication proactively addresses anticipated concerns or questions from recipients are proactively addressed in these confidentiality measures, and the potential benefits of the study. The formal

permission request explicitly seeks authorization to proceed, emphasizing the pivotal role of their support in ensuring the research’s success.

Permission to conduct the study

In November 2024, before data collection, the researcher will obtain necessary permissions from the relevant authorities, including the research adviser, the Dean of The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., and the top management of DepEd Davao Occidental Division through the appropriate channels. This involved submitting a comprehensive research proposal outlining study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher will provide detailed information about the study’s purpose, goals, and methods for data collection, analysis, and reporting. Furthermore, in January 2025, immediately after the colloquium, the researcher will take steps to ensure that all participants are fully informed about the study, their rights, and the nature of their involvement. Informed consent will be obtained from each participant before participating in the study. The researcher is committed to data accuracy and completeness during the last week of January 2025. Questionnaires will be distributed and retrieved using a standardized and systematic approach, ensuring reliability in collecting participant responses.

Collation and statistical treatment of data

The researcher will take time to manage the data. She will ensure that accurate data gathered will be sorted accordingly through Microsoft Excel and later transferred to JASP. All necessary information will be collected. Consistency will also be considered to make the problem’s statement relevant. Reliability and validity will be reviewed to lessen the degree of error in the analysis. This section outlines the statistical techniques employed to address the research problems, emphasizing the justification for grouping variables and the choice of inferential analysis methods. To examine the effects of English teaching approaches on learners’ literacy engagement and performance, the variable labeled ‘Pedagogical Approach’ was computed as a composite mean derived from five core indicators. This composite score represented the extent of pedagogical strategies used in English instruction. To categorize respondents meaningfully, the continuous variable ‘Pedagogical Approach’ was transformed into three discrete groups: Low, Moderate, and High. This classification was done through quantile-based binning (tertiles), enabling a balanced case distribution across the instructional levels. Quantile-based grouping is a recognized practice that aims to explore differences in outcomes based on levels of implementation (Field, 2021; Gravetter Wallnau, 2020).

Categorical Transformation of Likert-Scale Mean Scores

Mean Score Range	Category	Description
1.00 – 2.33	Low	Indicates minimal or weak implementation of the teaching approach
2.34 – 3.66	Moderate	Represents average or fair implementation of the teaching approach
3.67 – 5.00	High	Reflects strong and consistent implementation of the teaching approach

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The data gathered from the research instrument were systemati-

cally analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statis-

tics, including means and standard deviations, were used to determine the extent of implementation of English teaching approaches and the level of learners' literacy engagement and performance. For inferential analysis, One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to examine significant differences in literacy outcomes across varying levels of pedagogical approaches. Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) post hoc test was subsequently conducted to identify specific group differences. All analyses were carried out at a 0.05 level of significance using appropriate statistical software.

Mean scores and standard deviation

Will be used to address statement problems number one, the extent of English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment, and number two, the importance of literacy engagement and performance.

Analysis of Variance

(ANOVA) was used to determine the impact of literacy engagement and performance when exposed to English Teaching Strategies in terms of pedagogical approaches, level of experience, and classroom environment (Tabachnick Fidell, 2019). By calculating the F-statistic, ANOVA helps identify if the observed mean differences are statistically significant or occurred by chance. This is crucial for understanding the most effective practices.

Post-hoc Analysis

If ANOVA results indicate significant differences, post-hoc tests (such as Tukey's HSD) can be conducted to pinpoint precisely which groups differ. All data processing and analysis will be performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of statistical analyses addressing the research questions. It details the outcomes of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and post hoc analysis using Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test. These analyses determine significant differences in learners' literacy engagement and performance across different English teaching approaches, identifying which pedagogical strategies contributed to these differences. Empirical studies support the results interpretation and aligns with the research's conceptual framework. For clarity and academic rigor, descriptive statistics, inferential findings, and group analyses are presented in APA format. The findings provide insights into the pedagogical aspects of English instruction and their impact on student outcomes in the Sarangani District, Davao Occidental Schools Division.

3.1. Extent of The Implementation of English Teaching Approaches—Pedagogical strategies refer to teachers' instructional techniques and methodologies to enhance the learning experience. This includes differentiated instruction, communicative language teaching (CLT), scaffolding strategies, and formative assessments that align with the learners' diverse needs. In the present study, the domain of pedagogical strategies was operationalized through a five-

item scale, where respondents indicated the frequency and depth of their instructional practices. The mean scores derived from these indicators were used to classify respondents into Low, Moderate, and High implementation groups. Findings revealed that teachers with higher levels of pedagogical strategy implementation tended to engage in more interactive, learner-centered, and reflective teaching practices, consistent with the standards set by

the Department of Education (DepEd, 2023). Teaching experience levels were also considered, recognizing that the number of years in service and accumulated professional development significantly affect instructional competence. Teachers with extensive experience may exhibit greater confidence, classroom management skills, and curricular adaptability. According to Zhang et al. (2021), experienced educators are more likely to integrate innovative teaching approaches and tailor instruction to suit learner contexts. In the dataset, this domain was evaluated through self-assessed teaching exposure and effectiveness indicators. As the third domain, the classroom environment encompassed physical and psychological aspects of the learning setting that support English instruction. These include the availability of instructional resources, learner-teacher interaction quality, and the overall conduciveness of the classroom for language acquisition. Research shows that a supportive classroom climate enhances language engagement and reduces affective filters that hinder second language learning (Martin Rosa, 2023). In this study, the composite implementation of these three domains of English teaching approaches served as a basis for grouping respondents and analyzing their association with literacy engagement and performance outcomes. This structure enabled a systematic evaluation of how varying levels of teaching implementation impact learners' academic experience and language development,

These findings align with the literature emphasizing the interdependence of instructional quality, teacher expertise, and classroom context in influencing educational outcomes. For instance, Lopez and Gregorio (2023) found that pedagogical adaptability and innovation are often the first layers of reform teachers adopt to improve literacy outcomes. Meanwhile, Castro and Yambot (2022) emphasized that teaching ex-

perience must be complemented by ongoing professional development to be truly impactful. Espino and Caluza (2021) observed that a moderately supportive classroom environment, when combined with effective pedagogical strategies, creates optimal conditions for English language acquisition in public school contexts.

Summary of the Extent of Implementation of English Teaching Approaches

Table 1 summarizes the overall extent of the implementation of English teaching approaches across three major domains: pedagogical approaches, teacher experiences, and classroom environment. All domains were rated as "Moderately Extensive", with a computed overall mean of 3.23. Among the three, Pedagogical Approaches recorded the highest mean of 3.29, suggesting that instructional strategies such as using real-world examples, interactive activities, and collaborative learning tasks are relatively more consistently applied by teachers in the Sarangani District. This result underscores the importance placed by educators on learner-centered and contextually responsive instruction. The domain of Teacher Experiences yielded the lowest mean at 3.19, although still within the moderately extensive range. This may reflect teachers' awareness of their professional capacities, but also indicate a gap between experiential knowledge and its full integration into instructional innovation or differentiated learning practices. Classroom Environment followed closely with a mean of 3.23, highlighting a positive yet moderately established effort to maintain inclusive, resource-rich, and communicative English learning spaces.

perience must be complemented by ongoing professional development to be truly impactful. Espino and Caluza (2021) observed that a moderately supportive classroom environment, when combined with effective pedagogical strategies, creates optimal conditions for English language acquisition in public school contexts.

3.2. *Level of Learners' Literacy Engagement and Performance*—Learners' literacy en-

Table 1. Extent of the Implementation of English Teaching Approaches

No	English Teaching Approaches	n	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Pedagogical Approaches	146	3.29	Moderately Extensive
2	Teacher Experiences	146	3.19	Moderately Extensive
3	Classroom Environment	146	3.23	Moderately Extensive
Mean Average		146	3.23	Moderately Extensive

engagement and performance refer to the extent to which students actively participate in reading, writing, speaking, and listening tasks, and the measurable outcomes of their literacy development. Engagement involves motivation, attentiveness, and persistence in language-related activities, while performance is reflected in learners' demonstrated proficiency, comprehension, and application of English language skills. Together, these dimensions provide a holistic view of how students interact with and succeed in English learning tasks within the classroom context. Table 2 summarizes learners' literacy engagement and performance based on two key dimensions: self-reported literacy skills and peer interaction, reading comprehension and fluency, and motivation for reading. The overall average mean score of 3.19 indicates a "Moderately Ex-

tensive" level of engagement and performance in English literacy across both domains. Among the two components, Peer Interaction, Reading Comprehension and Fluency, and Motivation for Reading recorded the higher mean of 3.26, suggesting that social and motivational aspects of literacy learning play a substantial role in sustaining learner engagement. This implies that students respond positively to collaborative activities, peer discussions, and shared reading experiences that support reading fluency and intrinsic interest in language tasks. In contrast, the domain of Self-Reported Literacy Skills registered a slightly lower mean of 3.22, which, while still moderately extensive, indicates that learners have a somewhat conservative self-perception of their reading, writing, and speaking abilities in English.

Table 2. Learners' Literacy Engagement and Performance

No	Literacy Engagement and Performance	n	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Self-reported Literacy Skills	146	3.22	Moderately Extensive
2	Peer interaction, reading comprehension and fluency, and motivation for reading	146	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Mean Average		146	3.19	Moderately Extensive

These findings are aligned with Deci and Ryan's (2000) self-determination theory, which

emphasizes the importance of relatedness, competence, and autonomy in promoting motivation

and performance. Specifically, literacy environments that foster peer collaboration and authentic engagement with texts tend to generate higher levels of cognitive and emotional investment from learners. According to Domingo and Chavez (2023), students are more likely to report improved literacy outcomes when socially involved in reading communities promoting fluency and confidence. Furthermore, Cruz and Dela Peña (2022) assert that reading motivation and peer interaction are significant predictors of language proficiency, especially in second-language learning environments. These findings support the notion that while individual self-efficacy is important, interactive and socially enriched literacy activities may profoundly influence actual literacy engagement and perceived growth.

3.3. *Significant Difference in Literacy Engagement and Performance among Learners when Grouped According to the English Teaching Approaches Used*—Table 3 presents the results of a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to determine whether there are statistically significant differences in learners’ literacy engagement and performance when grouped according to the level of implementation of English teaching approaches. The

analysis yielded an F-value of 5.023 with a p-value of 0.008, indicating that the differences in mean literacy engagement and performance among the three groups, Low, Moderate, and High levels of English teaching approaches, are statistically significant at the 0.05 level. The between-group Sum of Squares (SS) was 1.507, and the Mean Square (MS) was 0.753 for 2 degrees of freedom (df), while the within-group (residual) Sum of Squares was 21.448 with a Mean Square of 0.150 across 143 degrees of freedom. The Type III Sum of Squares was used, which is appropriate in unbalanced designs and allows for an accurate estimation of main effects independent of other factors (Field, 2021). The significant p-value suggests that at least one group mean differs significantly from the others, confirming that the level of implementation of the English teaching approach has a measurable impact on learners’ literacy engagement and performance. This finding provides empirical support to the hypothesis that pedagogical quality determines language learning outcomes. The statistical result further justifies the application of a Tukey’s Honest Significant Difference (HSD) post hoc test to determine where these differences specifically lie among the groups.

Table 3. Difference in Literacy Engagement and Performance among Learners when Grouped According to the English Teaching Approaches Used

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p
Group	1.507	2	0.753	5.023	0.008
Residuals	21.448	143	0.150		

Note. Type III Sum of Squares. Significant at $p < .05$.

This result is consistent with the findings of Lopez and Gregorio (2023), who reported that higher implementation of learner-centered English teaching strategies significantly contributes to improvements in literacy proficiency

and academic motivation. Moreover, Martin and Dizon (2022) emphasized that teaching approaches grounded in interaction, feedback, and contextualized instruction lead to more engaged and literate learners, especially in public school

settings. The observed differences across pedagogical levels reinforce the position of Santiago (2021), who argued that instructional quality is not only a function of content delivery but also of how classroom strategies are aligned with learner needs and engagement levels. Decision on the Hypothesis Based on the findings of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), a statistically significant difference was found in learners' literacy engagement and performance when grouped according to the level of implementation of English teaching approaches, $F(2, 143) = 5.023$, $p = .008$ (see Table 8). Given that the p-value is less than the established significance level ($= 0.05$), the null hypothesis (H), which states that there is no significant difference in literacy engagement and performance among learners when grouped according to the English teaching approaches used, is rejected. This decision confirms the alternative hypothesis (H), which posits that there is a significant difference in literacy engagement and performance among learners across different levels of English teaching approaches. The result affirms that the extent to which English teaching approaches—comprising pedagogical strategies, teacher-level experiences, and classroom environment—are implemented has a measurable effect on students' literacy outcomes. The rejection of the null hypothesis highlights the importance of differentiating instructional practices and continuously improving teaching approaches to enhance student engagement and performance. It further provides empirical support for investing in teacher training and pedagogical innovation, as varying degrees of teaching quality significantly influence learner achievement in English literacy.

3.4. Components of English Teaching Approaches Significantly Influence Literacy Engagement and Performance Among Learners — Table 4 presents the results of a post hoc comparison using Tukey's HSD test, which was con-

ducted to determine which specific components of English teaching approaches, pedagogical Approaches (PA), Teacher Experiences (TE), and Classroom Environment (CA), significantly influence learners' literacy engagement and performance. This analysis was guided by the fourth research question and its corresponding hypothesis, which sought to determine whether any specific component of English teaching approaches statistically influences student outcomes. The post hoc results show that the Classroom Environment (CA) component significantly positively influences literacy engagement and performance when compared with Pedagogical Approaches (PA), with a mean difference of 0.250, a standard error of 0.080, and a p-value of 0.006. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the difference between CA and PA is statistically significant. This suggests that the quality of the classroom environment, such as the inclusivity, resource availability, and supportiveness of the space, plays a more substantial role in influencing learner outcomes than instructional methods alone. However, the differences between Classroom Environment (CA) and Teacher Experiences (TE) ($p = 0.118$), and between Pedagogical Approaches (PA) and Teacher Experiences (TE) ($p = 0.455$), were not statistically significant. This implies that while experience and pedagogical strategies contribute to literacy development, they may not independently predict variations in student performance when considered in isolation or in comparison to the learning environment. These findings confirm the rejection of the null hypothesis (H), which stated that none of the specific components of English teaching approaches significantly influence learners' literacy engagement and performance. The result affirms the alternative hypothesis (H), indicating that at least one component specifically the classroom environment, significantly influences the literacy outcomes of students.

Table 4. Components of English Teaching Approaches Significantly Influence Literacy Engagement and Performance Among Learners

Group 1	Group 2	Mean Difference	SE	df	t	p
CA	PA	0.250	0.080	143	3.142	0.006
CA	TE	0.157	0.079	143	1.992	0.118
PA	TE	-0.093	0.077	143	-1.199	0.455

Note. P-values adjusted using Tukey’s HSD for comparing a family of 3 estimates. CA = Communicative Approach; PA = Phonics Approach; TE = Traditional/Explicit.

The observed significance of classroom environment echoes the findings of Espino and Caluza (2021), who noted that positive, resource-enriched, and emotionally safe classroom conditions are directly linked to enhanced student motivation and academic engagement, particularly in English learning. Similarly, Santiago and Ramos (2022) emphasized that when students feel safe, heard, and supported in their classrooms, they are more likely to engage meaningfully in literacy tasks, take risks in language use, and improve their reading and writing fluency. Furthermore, Martin and Dizon (2022) argued that although pedagogical methods and teacher experience are critical foundations of quality instruction, their impact is significantly amplified or diminished by the surrounding learning environment. This reinforces the holistic view that effective English instruction must integrate strong classroom management, emotional support, and access to literacy-enhancing resources alongside sound pedagogy and teacher expertise. Based on the results of the Tukey’s HSD post hoc test presented in Table 9, it was found that a statistically significant difference exists between Classroom Environ-

ment and Pedagogical Approaches (mean difference = 0.250, $p = .006$). This p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating a meaningful disparity in their influence on student literacy engagement and performance. However, no significant difference was observed between Classroom Environment and Teacher Experiences ($p = .118$), nor between Pedagogical Approaches and Teacher Experiences ($p = .455$). Given the presence of at least one statistically significant difference among the components, the null hypothesis (H) is rejected. The findings support the alternative hypothesis (H), affirming that the Classroom Environment component significantly influences learners’ literacy engagement and performance when compared to pedagogical practices. This suggests that students benefit more from supportive, well-resourced, and inclusive learning environments than from instructional strategies alone. In summary, the significant influence of the classroom environment on learner outcomes underscores the need for a comprehensive approach to English instruction—one that integrates pedagogy, teacher development, and, crucially, the physical and psychological quality of the learning space.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions drawn from the results and findings discussed in the preceding chapter. It summarizes key insights regarding the extent of implementation of English teaching approaches—specifically pedagogical strategies, teacher experiences, and classroom

environment—and their influence on learners’ literacy engagement and performance. The conclusions are formulated based on the interpretation of statistical analyses, including descriptive measures, ANOVA results, and post hoc comparisons. Furthermore, this chapter outlines actionable recommendations for teachers, school administrators, and policy-makers to enhance instructional practices and optimize literacy outcomes among learners in the Sarangani District, Davao Occidental Schools Division. These recommendations are grounded in empirical evidence and are aligned with the broader goal of improving English language instruction within the public school context.

4.1. Findings—The extent of the implementation of English teaching approaches was found to be moderately extensive across all three domains. Among the components, Pedagogical Approaches recorded the highest mean score ($M = 3.29$), followed by Classroom Environment ($M = 3.23$) and Teacher Experiences ($M = 3.19$). This suggests that instructional strategies are the most frequently applied aspect of teaching English, while experiential and environmental supports are also moderately practiced. In terms of learners’ literacy engagement and performance, the study revealed that both dimensions, self—reported Literacy Skills and Peer Interaction, Reading Comprehension and Fluency, and Motivation for Reading, were rated as moderately extensive, with mean scores of 3.22 and 3.26, respectively. This indicates that learners perceive themselves as moderately confident and engaged in literacy tasks, particularly when activities involve peer collaboration and motivation through social reading practices. A statistically significant difference was found in learners’ literacy engagement and performance when grouped according to the level of English teaching approaches used: $F(2, 143) = 5.023$, $p = .008$. This result implies that the degree of implementation of teaching approaches, categorized into Low, Moderate, and High, affects learners’ academic outcomes in English, supporting the rejection of the null hypothesis for Statement of Problem No. 3. Post hoc analysis using Tukey’s HSD revealed that the Classroom Environment component significantly influenced literacy engagement and performance

compared to Pedagogical Approaches (Mean Difference = 0.250, $p = .006$). No significant differences were observed between Classroom Environment and Teacher Experiences ($p = .118$) or Pedagogical Approaches and Teacher Experiences ($p = .455$). This suggests that while all components contribute to instructional quality, the physical and psychological conditions of the classroom play a more crucial role in supporting learner outcomes. Overall, the findings affirm the importance of adopting a comprehensive and balanced approach to English language instruction, one that not only strengthens pedagogy and teacher development but also prioritizes the creation of supportive, inclusive, and resource-enriched classroom environments to foster higher levels of literacy engagement and performance.

4.2. Conclusions—English teaching approaches in the Sarangani District are moderately implemented, with pedagogical strategies being the most commonly applied among the components. However, teaching experience and classroom environment also play vital roles in influencing literacy instruction. Learners in this study reported moderate levels of literacy engagement and performance, particularly when collaborative and motivational reading activities were present, indicating the importance of social and affective dimensions of learning. There is a significant difference in literacy engagement and performance among learners when grouped according to the level of English teaching approaches used, validating the hypothesis that teaching quality is a determinant of learner out-

comes. Among the components examined, the classroom environment emerged as the only factor that significantly influenced literacy engagement and performance, emphasizing the need for emotionally safe, inclusive, and resource-rich learning spaces.

4.3. *Recommendations*—School administrators and curriculum leaders may provide targeted professional development programs to strengthen pedagogical practices, particularly in using contextualized, interactive, and technology-enhanced strategies. Ensure ade-

quate resources, foster a climate of inclusivity, and train teachers in positive behavior support and classroom management techniques to improve classroom environments. Policymakers may design literacy programs incorporating peer collaboration and motivational reading strategies to increase learners' interest and confidence in English. Further research may explore longitudinal outcomes of English teaching interventions, particularly those that integrate improvements in classroom environment with sustained pedagogical innovation.

5. References

- Alexander, K. L. (2024). Using intentional pairing and peer tutoring during structured literacy activities in inclusion classrooms. *Reading Teacher*, 77(6), 991–996. <https://doi.org/10.1002/trtr.2329>
- Allen Apanco, W. L. (2023). *English language learning teaching approaches in the elementary classroom* [Ed.D. Dissertation]. Trevecca Nazarene University. ProQuest LLC. http://gateway.proquest.com/openurl?url_ver=Z39.88-2004&rft_val_fmt=info:ofi/fmt:kev:mtx:dissertation&res_dat=xri:pqm&rft_dat=xri:pqdiss:30417264
- Alqahtani, R. M., & Alhamami, M. (2024). English as a foreign language teaching approaches in Saudi k-12 education: Teacher-centered or student-centered. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, 18(3), 817–824. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1430799.pdf>
- Alsawat, J. (2024). *Investigating Saudi world language English instructional approaches to empowering learner agency: A positioning theory perspective* [Ph.D. Dissertation]. Wayne State University. ProQuest LLC. https://gateway.proquest.com/openurl?url_ver=Z39.88-2004&rft_val_fmt=info:ofi/fmt:kev:mtx:dissertation&res_dat=xri:pqm&rft_dat=xri:pqdiss:30996282
- Andres, K. M., & Soriano, A. J. (2021). Challenges in establishing inclusive English classrooms in public secondary schools. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 9(2), 122–130.
- Anis, M., & Khan, R. (2023). Integrating multimodal approaches in English language teaching for inclusive education: A pedagogical exploration [Online Submission]. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 2(3), 241–257. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED631659.pdf>
- Arenas, R. M., & Villanueva, L. P. (2021). Encouraging extensive reading among high school learners: Implications for vocabulary and comprehension. *Philippine ESL Journal*, 17(2), 44–59.
- Ata, R., & Alpaslan, M. M. (2024). The role of digital literacy, epistemological belief and reading motivation and engagement in teaching 21st century skills. *International Journal of Information and Learning Technology*, 41(3), 304–317. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJILT-08-2023-0142>

- Avci, Ü., & Ergün, E. (2022). Online students' lms activities and their effect on engagement, information literacy and academic performance. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 30(1), 71–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2019.1636088>
- Barrantes, L. (2022). A humanistic perspective for the mixed-proficiency language class. *MEX-TESOL Journal*, 46(2). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1357806.pdf>
- Bautista, M. J., Del Mundo, C. R., & Javier, M. L. (2021). Exploring pedagogical renewal among experienced teachers in english instruction. *Philippine Journal of Teacher Education*, 13(1), 54–67.
- Chowdhury, T. A. (2021). Fostering learner autonomy through cooperative and collaborative learning. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 10(1), 89–95. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1320613.pdf>
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2022). *Research methods in education* (9th). Routledge.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2017). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th). Sage.
- Cruz, A. M., & Dela Peña, R. B. (2022). Collaborative reading and its effect on reading comprehension among junior high students. *Journal of Language and Literacy Education*, 14(1), 85–100.
- Datta, S., & Roy, S. (2024). Challenges of teaching english listening skills at the primary level in bangladesh. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 12(1), 3–12. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1412584.pdf>
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Delos Reyes, M. L., & Fernandez, R. C. (2022). Resource-enriched environments and their impact on english language teaching effectiveness. *Philippine Journal of Educational Research*, 15(1), 41–55.
- Domingo, A. J., & Chavez, E. S. (2023). Bridging the gap in writing and speaking proficiency among filipino learners. *Asian Journal of English Language and Pedagogy*, 12(1), 75–89.
- Espino, A. D., & Caluza, M. R. (2021). Creating supportive classroom environments for english learners in rural schools. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 99(2), 38–51.
- Field, A. (2021). *Discovering statistics using ibm spss statistics* (5th). SAGE Publications.
- Garcia, F. L., & Ortega, S. M. (2022). The impact of teaching experience on english instruction effectiveness in rural public schools. *Asian EFL Journal*, 29(3), 89–104.
- Gerrard, C. L., & Mollenkamp, M. (2024). Secondary music teachers' experiences in teaching english language learners. *Contributions to Music Education*, 49, 63–79. https://www.omea-ohio.org/general_and_subscription_infor.php
- Getenet, S., Cante, R., Redmond, P., & Albion, P. (2024). Students' digital technology attitude, literacy and self-efficacy and their effect on online learning engagement. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 21, Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00437-y>
- Gravetter, F. J., & Wallnau, L. B. (2020). *Statistics for the behavioral sciences* (10th). Cengage Learning.

- Hutchison, C. B., Ahlgrim-Delzell, L., Creech, T., Robertson, C., & Hguyen, N. (2018). A survey of expected versus actual pedagogical challenges experienced by international professors [Fall 2021]. *International Research and Review*, 8(1), 44–60. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1210833.pdf>
- Jiang, Y., & Sukying, A. (2024). Development of literacy engagement in chinese students with varying language proficiencies. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 12(3), 33–43. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1435015.pdf>
- Juárez-Díaz, C., Sandoval-Cruz, R. I., & Perales-Escudero, M. D. (2023). English teachers' approaches to e-teaching during the second term of emergency remote teaching. *MEXTESOL Journal*, 47(3). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1408054.pdf>
- Jung, C., & Choe, H. (2024). Professional identity of filipino english teachers teaching international students in a global city in the philippines. *English Teaching*, 79(2), 3–31. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1434440.pdf>
- Kukulka-Hulme, A., Lee, H., & Norris, L. (2021). Mobile technology and language learning: Reflections on the past, present and future. *ReCALL*, 33(3), 265–281. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0958344021000090>
- Li, C. Y., & Bautista, D. N. (2022). Exploring self-efficacy in english literacy skills: A case study among multilingual students. *International Journal of Language Education*, 6(3), 112–127. <https://doi.org/10.17509/ijle.v6i3.42018>
- Li, H., Zhu, S., Wu, D., Yang, H. H., & Guo, Q. (2023). Impact of information literacy, self-directed learning skills, and academic emotions on high school students' online learning engagement: A structural equation modeling analysis. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(10), 13485–13504. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11760-2>
- Liao, H., & Li, Y. (2023). Intercultural teaching approaches and practices of chinese teachers in english education: An exploratory mixed methods study. *Language Teaching Research*, 27(5), 1293–1324. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168820971467>
- Liu, X., Zhou, M., & Guo, J. (2023). Effects of efl learners' perceived social support on academic burnout: The mediating role of interaction engagement. *SAGE Open*, 13(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231212725>
- Lopez, J. P., & Gregorio, C. R. (2023). Examining the integration of learner-centered pedagogy in english language teaching. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Educational Development*, 13(1), 22–37.
- Lopez, M. E., & Ignacio, M. C. (2023). Digital readiness and instructional use of educational technology among rural secondary teachers. *Philippine Journal of Educational Technology*, 9(1), 45–59.
- Martin, J. T., & Dizon, M. R. (2022). Instructional quality and student literacy engagement in secondary english classrooms. *Philippine Journal of Language Teaching*, 56(2), 112–128.
- Navarro, C. D., & Ramirez, L. V. (2023). Classroom material availability and student motivation in english learning. *Journal of Language and Education Policy*, 7(1), 77–92.
- Ng, W. S., & Yu, G. (2023). The impacts of dialogic interaction to engage students in peer assessment. *Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 32(1), 53–64. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40299-021-00633-2>
- Perez, A. L., & Santos, R. M. (2021). Real-world application in esl classrooms: Enhancing relevance and learner retention. *Asian EFL Journal*, 28(4), 101–119.

- Reyes, P. D., & Mendez, A. F. (2023). Bridging experience and innovation: Cpd needs among mid-career english teachers. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 14(1), 15–27. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1401.02>
- Rivera, C. J. (2023). Building reading motivation through peer influence: A case study of filipino secondary learners. *Philippine Journal of Educational Psychology*, 18(2), 44–59.
- Rowe, L. W., Ridley, J., Borkowski, M. E., Jackson, S. E., & Hikida, M. (2024). Engaging with engagement: Interrogating preservice teachers' theories of engagement in their literacy planning and reflection. *Action in Teacher Education*, 46(2), 114–129. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01626620.2023.2293184>
- Santiago, B. M. (2021). Aligning teaching strategies with learner engagement: Implications for literacy achievement. *Southeast Asian Journal of Educational Research*, 8(3), 87–101.
- Santiago, B. M., & Ramos, L. A. (2022). Classroom climate and literacy outcomes in filipino esl settings. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educational Research*, 10(3), 77–93.
- Santos, J. P. (2021). Classroom emotional climate and learner engagement in english instruction. *International Journal of Educational Psychology*, 10(3), 185–198. <https://doi.org/10.17583/ijep.2021.6783>
- Serrano, K. T. (2021). Reflective teaching practices among experienced esl educators in the philippines. *International Journal of Education and Development*, 10(4), 203–219.
- Shotte, G. (2024). Widening and narrowing pedagogical spaces: Imperatives for english language teaching approaches. *Annual International Conference of the Bulgarian Comparative Education Society (BCES)*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED656181.pdf>
- Soriano, M. T., & Liwanag, M. J. (2021). Oral reading fluency and learner confidence in esl classrooms. *Asia Pacific Journal of English Language Teaching*, 9(3), 113–125.
- Sukavatee, P., & Khlaisang, J. (2023). A survey of research into english teaching approaches and instructional media in thailand. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 16(2), 752–769. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1401314.pdf>
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2019). *Using multivariate statistics* (7th). Pearson.
- Tan, J. F., & Ramos, K. L. (2022). Contextualized teaching in philippine english classrooms: Practices and challenges. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 13(1), 122–131. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1301.15>
- Tarrayo, V. N. (2023). Navigating the gender dimensions in english language teaching: Perceptions of senior high school teachers in the philippines. *Pedagogy, Culture and Society*, 31(5), 933–953. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681366.2021.1966080>
- Tarrayo, V. N., & Salonga, A. O. (2023). Queering english language teaching: Insights from teachers in a philippine state university. *Critical Inquiry in Language Studies*, 20(4), 360–385. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15427587.2022.2112532>
- Wolgast, A. (2023). The impact of adults' used skills on their self-evaluated skills and social lives over time. *European Journal of Psychology and Educational Research*, 6(2), 97–118. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1392595.pdf>
- Yim, S. Y., & Lim, E. Y. (2024). English teacher competency: A study with different school levels and teaching experience. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 44(2), 219–233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02188791.2023.2291986>
- Ylonfoun, A. L. E. (2023). *Beninese high school english teachers' prior english writing experiences: Implications for teaching writing in english* [Ph.D. Dissertation]. Indiana University

of Pennsylvania. ProQuest LLC. http://gateway.proquest.com/openurl?url_ver=Z39.88-2004&rft_val_fmt=info:ofi/fmt:kev:mtx:dissertation&res_dat=xri:pqm&rft_dat=xri:pqdiss:30313937

- Zhang, B. (2021). A comparison between pedagogical approaches in uk and china. *Journal of Comparative and International Higher Education*, 13(5), 232–242. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1326691.pdf>
- Zhang, Y. (2024). Factors influencing students' integration into english classrooms in ecologically fragile environments: An analysis. *International Journal of Web-Based Learning and Teaching Technologies*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJWLTT.336854>